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Second report on targeted new fieldwork and results

Deliverable Report

D8.7

WP8 - Targeted fieldwork surveys and alignment at EU level

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1 Authors and acknowledgements

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2 Glossary

EBC – Exhaled Breath Condensate

EU – European Union

GSA – General Survey Approach

HBM – Human Biomonitoring

HES – Health Examination Survey

HSA – Hotspot Approach

IC – Internal Call

ODC – Other Direct Cost

PAH – Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

PFAS – Per-/poly-fluoroalkyl substances

PI – Principal Investigator

PM – Person Month

SOP – Standard Operating Procedure

WP – Work Package

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3 Abstract/Summary

The work undertaken in Work Package 8 (WP8) for the first three years of the HBM4EU project have significantly contributed to harmonising Human Biomonitoring studies across the EU. The main aim of the WP is to collect biomonitoring data across Europe in order to determine exposure to the HBM4EU priority lists of substances either in the general population or via an occupational setting.

Task 8.1 focused on developing and implementing a sampling framework which could deliver the first EU wide harmonised Human Biomonitoring programme. The outcome was the inclusion of 33 studies from 21 countries representing north, south, east and west Europe. 27 studies across three age groups (children, teenagers/adolescents and adults) have completed sample collection, a further 4 expect to complete fieldwork by December 2019 and the remaining 2 will not complete before March and September 2020. The priority substances which will be analysed for each group is as follows: children – phthalates/DINCH and flame retardants; teenagers – phthalates/DINCH and per-/poly-fluorinated compounds; adults – cadmium, bisphenols and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH).

Task 8.2 has provided the logistics and platform for time trend analysis of exposure to 1st list of priority substances covering 3 time periods (2006-2010, 2011-2012 and 2014- 2019). For the first time-period, the trend analysis was restricted to literature review of studies with DINCH data. DEMOCOPHES partners were invited to provide their biobank samples to facilitate time trend analysis for 2011-2012. A total of 10 partners have agreed to provide samples for analysis and where necessary have obtained additional required ethical approval. Partners are currently in the process of agreeing the approved laboratory to undertake their sample analysis. The final time-period will be addressed by the results from the aligned studies (Task 8.1). The analysis for the priority substances in the collated DEMOCOPHES samples will follow the same principles as that outlined for Task 8.1 above.

Task 8.3 is being undertaken within Task 15.2 and has adopted a two-pronged approach whereby a 'general survey approach' (GSA) which includes the analysis of pesticides (from the 2nd round priority substances) in samples collected in activities in Task 8.1, is combined with the initially envisaged 'hotspot approach' (HSA) in Task 15.2. Sample collection for parent: child pairs during non-spraying stage (Phase 1) is currently in progress and should be completed by February 2020.

Task 8.4 is investigating the feasibility of integrating HBM into a national/regional Health Examination Survey (HES). Therefore, a German study (financed through the Internal Call (IC) in 2018) and the Finnish study of school children are currently undertaking the fieldwork using the HBM4EU protocols and guidance documents developed in WP7 as far as is practicable. Sample collection for both studies is expected to be completed in 2020 so the identification of obstacles and opportunities from integrating HBM into HES will commence thereafter.

Task 8.5 developed its first occupational study to assess occupational exposures to Chromium (VI) in the welding, Cr(VI) electroplating and other surface treatment settings. Blood, urine and exhaled breath were collected from the workers. Sample collection was completed this year and analysis of most samples has also taken place. The data is currently being compiled for statistical analysis which will be completed by February 2020. Preparation is underway for a second phase of occupational studies to address (i) diisocyanates in the manufacturing and repair of vehicles, diisocyanate-based glues in different sectors, and construction sector which includes different sources of diisocyanates exposure (floorings, insulation) and (ii) different priority compounds (including metals, flame retardants and phthalates) in the e-waste industry.

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4 Introduction

The aim of this deliverable is to provide an update of the activities undertaken within WP8 with regards to harmonising the fieldwork national Human Biomonitoring both for population and occupational studies. The focus of the report includes updates on the following activities:

- aligning of national or regional HBM: population and occupational studies to produce comparable HBM data for the priority chemicals
- accessing samples from biobanks and additional information for the determination of time-trend analysis
- undertaking a mixtures study building on the frameworks, SOPs and protocols developed in Y2
- initiating two studies to investigate the feasibility of including HBM in health examination surveys/studies
- completing the collection of occupational samples for the determination of chromate and concomitant PFAS exposure.
- commencing the development of the second occupational studies on diisocyanate and e-waste.

These activities will contribute to the building of HBM platform for the EU (Pillar 2).

The report will also highlight some of the challenges experienced and their impact on the agreed course of work including any amendments to the work programme.

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5 Task Updates

5.1 Task 8.1: Alignment of national studies

Task 8.1 has sought to align studies that will/have collect(ed) blood and urine samples from three age groups (children (6-11 years), teenagers (12-19 years) and adults (20-39 years)) of the general population for the period 2014-2019 across Europe. As such this task has built on existing capacity where possible so have included studies that:

- have already collected samples so will contribute biobank samples to be analysed in the HBM4EU programme;
- are ongoing and will complete sample collection within the stipulated time frame; and
- will undertake new studies within the timeframe.

The sample strategy and framework is described in detail in D8.4 (Strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results). In total, there are 33 studies from 21 countries providing EU coverage (north, south, east and west); 11 per age group (refer to Table 1). The priority substances to be analysed in the respective age groups are given in Table 2.

Table 1: Number of studies and provisional number of samples collected per age group by EU region

Age Group		North	South	East	West
Children (6-11years)	No. of studies	2	3	3	3
	No. of samples	600	598	864	900
Teenagers (12-19years)	No. of studies	2	3	3	3
	No. of samples	484	548	900	900
Adults (20-39years)	No. of studies	3	2	2	4
	No. of samples	742	600	600	1165

Table 2: Priority substances to be analysed in the age groups

Children	Teenagers	Adults
Phthalates/DINCH	Phthalates/DINCH	Cadmium
Flame retardants	PFAS	Bisphenols
		PAHs

To date 27 studies across three age groups (children, teenagers/adolescents and adults) have completed sample collection, a further 4 expect to complete fieldwork by December 2019 and the remaining 2 will not complete before March and September 2020. Currently it is unlikely that 2 studies completing the fieldwork in 2020 will be able to provide data to be included in the statistical analysis which is scheduled to commence by May/June 2020.

Principal Investigators (PIs) are presently selecting the laboratories to undertake analysis of their samples which has resulted in several partners experiencing issues with regards to payment for the (analytical) service. Hence the TL has prepared a guidance document detailing the ways to deal with budgetary issues relating to chemical analysis which is now available to all PIs.

Task 8.1 is also in process of selecting aligned studies for the implementation of the analysis of effect biomarkers. The aim is to test the hypothesis that measurement of effect biomarkers may enhance the interpretation of exposure biomarker measurements. The effect biomarkers under consideration for this proof of concept study were selected based on extensive literature review

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and available AOP wiki information performed/collected within WP13 and WP14. In parallel, work is also underway to select aligned studies for the implementation of some of the 2nd set of priority substances (arsenic, pesticides, UV-filters, mycotoxins and acrylamide). Further details of this novel work can be found in D8.8: Progress report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results.

Thus far, this work has highlighted that there are many issues which drive the implementation of a HBM programme in a country such as the varying national interests and priorities. Hence it is imperative that these challenges are overcome to continue to build this initiative which seeks to facilitate the comparability of data for human exposure to chemicals across Europe.

Deliverables

D8.8: Progress report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results – Due date: November 2019

AD8.1: Studies implementing second set priority chemicals and/or biomarkers of effect – Due date: January 2020 (subject to change)

5.2 Task 8.2: Use of existing samples from biobanks

Task 8.2 aims to undertake time trend analysis covering 3 time periods (2006-2010, 2011-2012 and 2014- 2019) to ascertain exposure of the EU population to some of the 1st list of priority chemicals. The review of DINCH data for the first time-period has been completed and currently grey literature reviews are in progress for substances in the 2nd list of priority substances. This is expected to be completed in 2020.

DEMOCOPHES partners were invited to provide their biobank samples to facilitate time trend analysis for 2011-2012. The DEMOCOPHES biobank includes urine samples collected in 2011/12 from mother (up to 45 years)/children (5-11years) pairs in 17 European countries. Some substances such as BPA and Cd have already been analysed in some countries and these data can be made available for the time trend analyses. The new analyses are required to provide retrospective exposure information for a set of chemicals to be compared with data collected in women and children 2014-2019 for the same set of chemicals and to facilitate time trend analysis. In line with the work undertaken in Task 8.1, every effort was made to ensure that the 4 regions (north, south, east and west) were represented. Table 3 contains a list of those countries that have agreed to submit DEMOCOPHES samples together with the substances which they are most interested in analysing.

TL 8.2 has worked in close collaboration with TL 8.1 to ensure that the priority for substances to be analysed in the DEMOCOPHES samples is aligned to the rest of the analysis in “alignment of national studies”. The decreasing order of priority for analysis of substances in the DEMOCOPHES samples is as follows:

1. DINCH metabolites in children (a set of phthalate metabolites have already been analysed within the DEMOCOPHES project).
2. BPS and BPA in women. BPA is already analysed in 6 countries (Belgium, Denmark, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden).
3. PAH metabolites in women.
4. Organophosphate flame retardants metabolites, however, as yet there are no approved laboratories to perform the analysis.

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A total of 10 partners (refer to Table 3) have agreed to provide samples for analysis and where necessary have obtained the required ethical approval. Partners are currently in the process of agreeing the approved laboratory to undertake their sample analysis. The final time-period will be addressed by the results from the aligned studies (Task 8.1). The analysis for the priority substances in the collated DEMOCOPHES samples will follow the same principles as that outlined for Task 8.1 above. TL 8.2 will work in collaboration with WP10 to ascertain the basic set of personal information which is required to undertake the trend analysis.

Further details of this summary of Task 8.2 activities can be found in D8.6: Second report on biobank activities.

Table 3: Selected substances to be analysed in DEMOCOPHES samples from participating countries

Country	Region	Maximum no. of mother: child samples	DINCH in children	Flame retardants in children	Phthalates in children	BPA in women	BPS in women	BPF in women	PAH in women
Denmark*	North	240							
Sweden	North	200	X			X	X		X
Slovenia	South	240	X	X	X		X	x	x
Spain	South	120				X	X	X	
Cyprus	South	120	X			X	X	X	X
Czech Republic	East	240				X	X	X	
Poland*	East	240							
Belgium	West	120				X	X	X	
Germany	West	240	X	X					X
Luxembourg	West	120	X			X	X	X	X

*- to be confirmed

Deliverables:

D8.6: Second report on biobank activities - Due date: November 2019

AD8.3: Summary report of T8.2 activities – Due date: March 2020

5.3 Task 8.3: Targeted fieldwork for mixtures

Task 8.3 is being undertaken within Task 15.2 and has adopted a two-pronged approach whereby in a 'general survey approach' (GSA) the analysis of pesticides (from the 2nd round priority substances) in samples collected in activities in Task 8.1 is combined with the initially envisaged 'hotspot approach' (HSA) in Task 15.2.

Five countries (Spain, Czech Republic, Hungary, Netherlands, Latvia) are participating in the hotspot study and have received ethical approval. 50 parent:child pair of urine samples will be collected in each country. Phase 1 (non-spraying) has commenced in Spain and is scheduled to take place October 2019 – February 2020. Phase 2 (spraying) is scheduled to take place April – August 2020. The control for this survey will be extracted from Task 8.1. Switzerland will collect

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urine samples from adults for a single time point. Laboratories to undertake the sample analyses have been selected.

Deliverables

AD15.8 - Report of fieldwork phase and first impressions of the suspect screening – Due date: October 2020

5.4 Task 8.4: Targeted fieldwork in combining HBM and HES

Task 8.4 is investigating the feasibility of integrating HBM into HES programmes which exist at national or regional level within European countries. The aim is to use the guidelines and protocols developed in WP7 for HBM and previously prepared protocols by EHES for HES as far as practicable to do the fieldwork and sample processing.

Combining HBM and HES was the topic of an IC in early 2018; a German study was successful in being awarded funding in late 2018. This year the PI obtained ethical approval for the work and have appropriately adapted the sampling protocols (including preparation of sample containers and processing of the collected samples) from HBM4EU. The PI has adapted and translated the HBM4EU questionnaires for those selected priority substances (phthalates, inorganic and organic arsenic and mercury) which has subsequently being integrated into the HES questionnaire tool. Due to a number of issues including delay in pre-financing, the study has being delayed and will only start sample collection (400 participants) in December 2019. Given this, an extension to September 2020 will be sought from the coordinator.

In 2019, the Finnish study obtained ethical approval and has recruited 7 schools (target almost 950 students to achieve 300 sample population of 10-12 year olds) to commence sample collection. These 7 schools are located in the urban part of the city of Kuopio. Due to the requirements from the ethical committee, the study protocol had to be amended substantially: 1) no blood samples can be collected, so the work is now limited to urine samples; 2) sample collection cannot be conducted as part of regular school health check-up visit. Therefore, the sampling kits will be sent to children's residences where the samples will be taken and returned to the laboratory. Given this additional activity the conversion of some PM to ODC (for mailing of the sample kits) may be required.

For the Finnish study, principals have been contacted. All written materials (questionnaire, information leaflet, informed consent, data protection leaflet and invitation letter) have been prepared. The transfer of the questionnaire to a web-based system is almost complete and sampling materials have been ordered. School visits were planned to start at the end of November 2019 and end by the Christmas holidays. Due to a strike in the Finnish mail service, which will commence on 11 December and may last from 2-4 weeks, the start of the sample collection had to be delayed and is now planned to start after the Christmas break in January 2020. This will delay the completion of the sample collection by couple months.

Deliverables

None

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5.5 Task 8.5: Targeted occupational studies with added EU value

Task 8.5 efforts have been focussed on undertaking occupational studies with a policy relevance. Hence the first occupational study to assess occupational exposures to Chromium (VI) in the welding, Cr(VI) electroplating and other surface treatment settings using harmonised methods and questionnaires was developed. The chromate study included 7 countries (France, Finland, United Kingdom, Portugal, Italy, Poland, Belgium). Blood, urine and exhaled breath condensate (EBC) were collected from the workers. Sample collection was completed this year and analysis of most samples has also taken place. A report was produced (D8.5: Initial report on occupational studies) providing further details of the work. The data is currently being compiled for statistical analysis which will be completed by February 2020. Given that the results are not yet available, a request was made to delay D8.9 (Progress report of targeted occupational studies) which has been approved by the coordinator and EC. Data analysis will be done in collaboration with WP10.

Four mini-reviews were undertaken in 2018 which informed the development of further occupational studies. Preparation is in progress for the second phase of occupational studies to address the following:

- (i) diisocyanates in the manufacturing and repair of vehicles, diisocyanate-based glues in different sectors, and construction sector which includes different sources of diisocyanates exposure (floorings, insulation). 8 countries will participate in this study (refer to Table 4 for partners involved).
- (ii) different priority compounds including metals, flame retardants and phthalates in the e-waste industry. Partners specified in Table 4 will participate in this study.

The study protocol is being prepared and will be submitted in January 2020 (AD8.2). It is envisaged that smaller countries such as Luxembourg and Latvia/Lithuania may not collect a full set of samples. Preliminary investigations have highlighted the high cost of sample transportation hence this may have been underestimated and will need to be addressed again.

Table 4: Countries participating in the diisocyanate and e-waste occupational studies

Diisocyanate	E-waste
FIOH	RUMC
HSL/IOM	LNS
TNO	INSA/ESTeSL
KuLeuven	NIOM
INRS	RSU
	IPASUM
	NPHI
	LSMU

Deliverables

D8.5: Initial Report on occupational studies - APPROVED

D8.9: Progress report on targeted occupational studies – Due date: February 2020

AD8.2: Detailed research plan for the occupational diisocyanate and E-waste study – Due date: January 2020